

IMPLEMENTATION OF LEAN CONSTRUCTION PRINCIPLES FOR A COLLECTIVE ENHANCEMENT OF PROJECT SUCCESS IN UGANDA

F. SSALI¹, N.S. MATSILIZA², S. MOYO³, H. ALINAITWE⁴, D.N. NSHEKANBO⁵ and S.H.P. CHIKAFALIMANI⁶

^{1,2,3,6} Department of Entrepreneurial Studies and Management, Durban University of Technology, Durban, South Africa.

^{4,5} College of Engineering, Design, Arts and Technology, Makerere University, Kampala, Uganda.

Email: ¹ssalifrankie@gmail.com, ²shirleymats2@gmail.com, ³dvcrie@dut.ac.za, ³smoyo962@gmail.com,

⁴alinaitwe_h@cedat.mak.ac.ug, ⁵dnaturinda@cedat.mak.ac.ug ⁶samuelc@dut.ac.za

Abstract:

Globally, the cost of construction is escalating and the related industry practices are still regarded as wasteful. Despite the benefits that come along with lean construction concepts and practices worldwide, its adoption generally is still at the incipient stage, particularly in developing countries like Uganda. Moreover, many projects have experienced several problems like; time delays, cost overruns and the generation of massive amounts of waste. Many construction companies in the country are being faced with challenges of non-value adding activities that need to be addressed for the industry to gain substantial benefits from the processes. This research investigates the implementation of lean construction principles for a collective enhancement of project success for Uganda as a developing country. A systematic review methodology was adopted to critically identify the diverse lean construction concepts, and a contextual rationalization of the lean construction benefits appropriate for Uganda was developed. Secondary data was used for the study. Data was collected from published journal papers, conference papers, text books and was analysed. From the study it is evident that Uganda's construction industry has not yet substantially embraced the lean construction principles.

Keywords: Lean Construction, Project Success, Waste Reduction, Uganda

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

The construction industry is an important sector that generally produces small and mega projects globally (Jiang and Wong, 2016). The construction industry is faced with several challenges, in Africa and globally, which are certainly of great concern to solve (Sawhney, Agnihotri, and Virendra, 2014). Over time, the construction industry has been criticized for being wasteful, unsafe, fragmented, inefficient, and ineffective (Tezel and Nielsen, 2013). Additionally, Muhwezi et al., (2013) observed that wastage of resources in construction extends to labour, time, materials, capital and machinery. The underlying problems as a result drastically affect the overall project deliverables such as time, cost, and quality in the long run. Tabish and Jha (2012) assert that the specific project deliverables of schedule, cost and quality were considered to be the "iron triangle" which is a criteria for determining the success of a project. According to Ramlee et al., (2016) a project is considered as successful in the construction industry when it is completed on time, within budget and the quality is satisfied.

Lean construction as a set of principles can be used to moderate some of the identified construction project success concerns. According to Koskela et al., (2018) lean construction originated as a set of countermeasures to problems such as; delays in construction delivery, escalating project costs, and most importantly client disappointment which could lead to contractual frustration.

Bajjou, Chafi and En-Nadi (2017) postulate that creating value and eliminating waste through the adoption of lean techniques have shown a great ability to improve the traditional production system in Africa. According to Emuze and Ungerer (2014) change in the construction processes is vital as a result of the several project performance related concerns that have made news in the media in the form of fatalities and project time overruns in the South Africa's industry.

Moreover, according to Abarinda, Kibwami and Tutesigensi (2020) this concept is very vital in improving the project timely delivery. However, the Lean concept is still not yet appropriately ventured into Uganda's construction industry. Moreover, according to Johansen and Walter (2007), the construction industries all over the world have gained significant benefits through the utilisation of the lean construction techniques, especially in the more developed countries such as: Australia, Brazil, Denmark, Finland, Singapore, the United Kingdom, and the United States of America.

Lai and Huili-Lin (2017) demonstrate that according to systems theory, components of each system are hierarchical and inter-dependent in that one component cannot function without the support of the other. The purpose of this paper was to review and analyse literature on lean construction without a view to identifying research gaps. Generic outcomes from the systematic literature review will be used to embolden lean implementation in Uganda's construction industry.

1.2 Problem Statement

Construction projects generally have a very poor record of project success in terms of completion within cost, time and quality objectives (Sarhan et al., 2019). In Uganda, this is superlatively evidenced with the unsuccessful projects exhibited by time overruns, cost overruns and inadequate quality (Muzaale and Auriacombe, 2018).

Emuze and Ungerer (2014) demonstrate limited awareness of lean construction in South Africa and Africa at large amongst practitioners. Furthermore, in Uganda, Alinaitwe, Apolot and Tindiwesi (2013) illustrate that awareness is a challenge in the industry. Lean construction principles have not been explored and tried to their full potential. According to various studies, there is not much emphasis on lean construction and project success in Africa and in Uganda's construction industry in particular. Hence this research on lean construction is an attempt to address this gap.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Lean Concepts and Principles

Aziz and Hafez (2013) demonstrate that since the 1950s, the Toyota motor company has magnificently applied lean production or Toyota production system as they evolved over the years. Toyota's production system is composed of two main pillars: Just in Time (JIT) flow and Autonomation (Aziz and Hafez, 2013) as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Beginning of lean production (Source: Aziz and Hafez, 2013)

According to Chung and Mutis (2019), lean construction concepts are processes or measures that minimise non-value adding activities and also make sure that the value adding activities are extensively controlled in order to increase productivity. Therefore, lean construction is all about management and improvement of the construction processes to profitably deliver what the client needs through the elimination of waste in the construction stream. This can be done by using the right principles, resources and measures to deliver things right the first time (Dehdasht et al., 2020). Thus, the major intention of lean construction as a concept is to decrease wastage whilst increasing on the value of the outputs. Dehdasht et al., (2020) additionally emphasise that continuous improvement, high levels of user focus, improved commitment and communication, value for money, and the betterment of both project management and supply chain are more of the additional benefits of lean construction once incorporated in the production processes.

Aziz and Hafez (2013), support the adoption of a number of key techniques of lean construction by practioners and stakeholders throughout the project stages. In the earlier project stage of its implementation, in the 90s three principles of production philosophy were proposed to be used. These included tools circles, a manufacturing method and a management philosophy. One of the examples of the key concepts is Just-In-Time (JIT) which according to Ahmed and Sobuz (2019) is a means of producing only what is needed; when it is needed, and in the quantity

needed. This is a pull system that addresses the definite customers' demand and consequently leads to better equipment productivity.

According to Von-Rosing (2015), Figure 2, below, shows "Just in Time" in conjunction with "Jidoka", a Japanese principle in waste reduction. In Figure 2, Von-Rosing (2015) illustrates that the roof can only be held up by Just-In-Time (JIT) and Jidoka, which is realized through people's exertions and the lessening of waste. Åhlström (2015) discusses Jidoka, in that an operative is authorised to take control and stop the production line if something incorrect is detected or getting out of order. This could be anything, ranging from a quality problem or alert, equipment fault, health and safety worry or overwork of individual components. According to Soliman (2016), Jidoka is discussed as a principle of creating or ensuring quality for customers. Henceforward encouraging inspections for quality, and consequently calling for 'making it right the first time'. The general view of minimising waste in the industry gave rise to the implementation of the major lean principle, which states that any activity that does not add value to the processes must be cut off.

Figure 2: Project success house through waste reduction: Source (Von-Rosing, 2015)

Other lean principles include: Total Quality Control (TQC), Total Productive Maintenance (TPM), Employee Involvement (EI), Continuous Improvement (CI), benchmarking, time-based competition, Concurrent Engineering (CE), value-based strategy (or management), visual management, and re-engineering.

In addition, Felipe and Luci (2018) highlight eleven Lean Construction techniques to be implemented in the mainstream processes and their sub processes in the construction industry. These techniques include the following:

Reducing the share of non-value adding activities whilst increasing focus on the value adding processes;

Increasing output value through methodical assessment and consideration of customer requirements;

Reduce project variability, minimise cycle time of operations, lessen the number of steps taken during the actual production;

Streamlining parts and linkages to avoid error, maximise output flexibility, increase process transparency, emphasis on the control of the complete processes, build continuous improvement into the processes, balance flow improvement with conversion improvement and benchmarking. Nevertheless, there are principles of lean construction, which postulate value from the clients' view, classify the value stream, make the value-creating flow, accomplish customer pull at the right time and pursue excellence for continuous improvement (Koskela et al., 2018).

In a survey, Alinaitwe (2009) simplified and depicted the key concepts of Lean Construction and since then these included: Just-In-Time (JIT), Total Quality Management (TQM), Business Process Re-engineering (BPR), Concurrent Engineering (CE) and Last Planner System (LPS); Teamwork and Value Based Management (VBM). These were identified as some of the commonly used techniques in the construction industry. Most of these techniques were found to be useful in ensuring waste reduction in the general construction industry worldwide. However, the mentioned techniques were not checked or tested on how compatible they could be with Uganda's construction industry.

2.2 Project Success

Alzahrani and Emsley (2013) refer to project success as "having results much better than expected or normally observed in terms of cost, schedule, quality, safety and participant satisfaction". Alzahrani and Emsley (2013) further suggest that construction project success is "having everything turn out as hoped". However according to Hanafi and Nawawi (2016) clients and their consultant's team relate success mostly to the accomplishment of quality objectives and owner satisfaction. Similarly, contractors, on the other hand, lay more emphasis on controlling costs, owners' satisfaction and in addition the relationship with subcontractors and skilled workers. Khaleefah and Alzobae (2016) describe a successful project in simplest terms, as "a project incorporating four basic facets namely: if it is delivered on-budget (monetary criterion), comes in on-schedule (time criterion), is used and accepted by the clients and users for whom the project was intended (client satisfaction criterion) and achieves all the objectives originally set for it (effectiveness criterion). Project success consequently largely looks at client satisfaction, project timely delivery, project delivery within a specific budget, and in a way that the overall set objectives positively affect the entire project.

Nonetheless, this concept remains somewhat of a conundrum as there is no conclusion on what the critical success criteria on construction projects despite several studies (Alzahrani and Emsley 2013) should be.

2.3 Critical Success Factors (CSF) for construction

Identifying critical success factors would assist in taking proactive measures for successful project management. Schedule, cost and quality performance is considered to be the “iron triangle” which is the criteria for determining the success of a project (Tabish and Jha, 2012). According to Ramlee et al., (2016), a project is considered as successful in the construction industry when it is completed on time, within budget and the quality is satisfied. The studies about the critical success factors and identification will as well be useful for effective management of all the various categories of construction projects, and consequently help to raise the overall level of productivity in the construction industry (Jari and Bhangale 2013). Khaleefah and Alzobae (2016) discuss the critical success factors that can be grouped under seven main categories. These include the following: (1) Project Management Factors; (2) Procurement-related Factors; (3) Client-related Factors; (4) Design team-related Factors; (5) Contractor-related Factors; (6) Project Manager-related Factors; and (7) Business and Work Environment related Factors (Khaleefah and Alzobae, 2016). However, in the literature reviewed there is little emphasis put on issues concerning lean construction and project success in Africa, and more so in the Ugandan construction industry. Hence this study opts to bridge-up the identified gap.

Moreover, according to Abarinda, Kibwami and Tutesigensi (2020), the lean construction concept is still not yet appropriately ventured into Uganda’s construction industry and yet most projects are not completed within their original contract set targets. Alinaitwe, Apolot, and Tindiwesi (2013) support the idea that there are high rates of cost and time overruns in Uganda’s construction industry and if not properly handled may lead to frustration in construction contracts. Most of the projects tendered for more especially government projects emerge to be expensive compared to similar projects. This to a given extent affects government spending and in the long run calls for higher government borrowing due to a lack of efficiency in the execution of public infrastructure development projects (Alinaitwe and Ayesiga 2013). Abarinda, Kibwami and Tutesigensi (2020) posit that such poor performance could be addressed by implementing lean construction principles. Nevertheless, Arif, Aini, Azmi and Bari (2012) demonstrate that Lean Construction has faced several challenges but that the challenges can be overcome if carefully handled. Womack and Jones (1996) recommended that lean production is able to minimise the overall cost of construction especially the indirect cost while still maintaining the quality standards and reducing production cycle times. It was posited that the level of knowledge on Lean Construction was not so high and there are concerns to learn and solve the construction problems in the work fields (Abarinda, Kibwami and Tutesigensi, 2020). As stipulated from the literature investigation on lean construction, it has been noticed that there is a limited number of frameworks for the implementation of lean construction techniques for project success in the industry. Comparison of lean construction requirements and project success in the construction is still lacking. There is the inadequate application of lean construction principles in construction projects during the project execution. Hence the aim of this paper is to contribute to improving the implementation of lean construction technology through a contextual rationalization of the benefits drawn from the critical literature review.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research approach

This study adopted a systematic literature review research design of published literature. Green (2005) suggests that a systematic literature review is an important scientific research approach that can be used to assess, summarize, and communicate the findings and implications of a large number of research publications on a particular subject. A systematic literature review is used to collect and examine a big number of research studies and publications correlating to an explicit subject matter to answer predefined questions, by integrating the general practical evidence from all the pertinent studies. This kind of literature review investigation by its nature is capable of addressing much broader questions than what single empirical studies could securely realise. Furthermore, a systematic review is much better in terms of providing more robust evidence compared to other research designs because it has the potential to deliver the most imperative applied implications. Therefore, for this study, a systematic literature review focused on reviewing available lean construction and project success related studies in the construction industry through different search engines and publications were adopted.

3.2 Selection criteria

The inclusive dates for the searches ranged from January, 2005 to January 2022 covering a total of 17 years, only English language books, conference papers and peer-reviewed journal papers were included. In addition, the search terms used were ‘‘Lean construction technology’’, ‘‘Project success in Uganda’’, and ‘‘Waste reduction’’. Furthermore, many of the sources excluded were papers focusing more on the warehousing and manufacturing environment lean processes, informal means of communication and unpublished materials.

Out of the 135 publications extracted from the initial search primarily, an extensive evaluation was done to ascertain whether the individual publications were appropriate for the systematic literature review. The preliminary evaluation criterion was to determine whether or not the publication was interrelated to the subject matter of lean construction implementation and project success. The additional scrutinizing procedure was to discover whether or not the publication was important to the scope of the study. An overall of 48 publications in Africa was found to be related and significant to the topic of study. In the past 15 years, seven related research papers were found to be on Uganda’s construction industry in particular.

Figure 3: Showing the lean construction document selection

Source (Ssali, et.al., 2022)

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

As shown in the figure above, only 5% of publications have been found to be in Uganda, 36% covering the rest of Africa and 59% for the rest of the world. Based on the analysis, it is clearly shown that there are fewer publications made on the subject matter in Africa and Uganda in particular. It is traced back to the fact that lean construction is still novel and has not yet been fully embraced in the African nations.

According to the study, a context demonstrating the benefits of lean construction technology from previous researchers was developed. The context clearly shows that according to research done from 2005 to 2018, lean construction techniques have definite benefits that have helped in solving the underlying problems of wastage and have added to the improvement of project success in the construction industry. The study further shows that benefits such as; reduced waste, increased productivity, improved quality, improved customer satisfaction, shortened schedules, and reduced costs have been found to be profound by the selected research under this systemic review. Furthermore, the underlying evaluated benefits suit the nature of the construction industry in the developing countries. And most importantly according to the researchers these benefits strategically help in improving the construction project success in terms of cost, time and quality.

However, all-through the research evaluated under this study, the major benefits echoed from the implementation of lean construction techniques have not been critically aligned together or contextualised; in order to support the developing countries in solving the underlying construction industry's escalating problems. Additionally, the benefits were not adequately aligned with the enhancement of project success generally. And in the due course the industries' key success factors including; timely delivery of projects, quality control and completion within budget are left wanting.

Table 1: Context showing benefits of lean construction from previous researchers

AUTHORS	BENEFITS
Luo et al., (2005)	• Minimise double handling and movement of equipment and workers
	• Balance team, coordinate flows
	• Take off material constraints,
	• Minimise variance in input
	• Minimise changeovers and difficult setups
	• Reduce interpersonal dynamics
Mossman (2009)	• Less waste
	• Eliminate cost
	• Increase productivity
	• Shorten schedules
	• Improve reliability
	• Improve quality
	• Improve client satisfaction
	• Increase predictability
	• Improvement to design to enhance buildability
	• Improved safety
Womack and Jones (2010)	• Meet the needs of the client.
	• Outline value from the project viewpoint.
	• Use flexible resources and adaptative planning in responding to opportunities and changing needs.
	• Use target costing and value.
Modi and Thakkar (2014)	• Labour reduction while maintaining or increasing output
	• Maximise the use of multi-skilled employees
	• Improve effective communication between stakeholders
	• Encourage collaboration
	• Encourages lean
Opeoluwa, Ayodeji, Aigbavboa and Mulongo (2018)	• Reduced waste
	• Efficient administration of materials
	• Improved whole-life cost
	• Improved customer satisfaction
	• Improved safety
	• Increased productivity
	• Improved risk management
	• Reduced project timetable
• Efficient communication among the client and construction team	
	• Improved Quality

Source: (Ssali, et.al., 2022)

Moreover according to the study, in Uganda particularly, negligible research has been made about lean construction. This has led to a traceable gap between lean construction knowledge, its implementation, and enjoyment of the benefits that come with its implementation. It can therefore be concluded that the current adoption and execution of lean construction technology to improve on project success in the Uganda’s construction industry is still in its infancy or its

very early stages. Stakeholders may not be aware of the potential benefits they stand to gain from value for money for their projects.

The major aim of this study thus, was to create awareness with a view to improving the implementation of lean construction through a contextual rationalization of the benefits drawn from the critical literature review for a collective enhancement of project success in Uganda.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The full implementation of lean construction in Uganda’s construction industry, in particular, still needs more effort and support from all the associated parties/stakeholders such as the education system, the consultants, interrelated authorities and the customers in the industry. Integrating strategic lean construction principles like reducing waste will increase the chances of project success in a developing country like Uganda.

Best practices in the value of implementing Lean Construction need to be adopted in order to address the prevailing construction project delivery related problems. Furthermore, the process of maximising value in the construction processes from start to finish of the project must be observed. This will assist in optimising the use of resources and reducing waste, thus creating sustainable enterprises and improving the services of the construction industry. Future work will focus on looking at creating sustainable futures and communities as aligned to the sustainable development goal 11, of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, aimed at “making cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable” (United Nations, 2015).

Graphical Abstract

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